

INFLUENCE ON FACULTY COMMITMENT OF EMPLOYEE OF DEEMED UNIVERSITY – TAMIL NADU

Dr. B. SUBATRA

Research Supervisor, Department of Commerce (B. Com PA) Government Arts and Science College, Thondamuthur, Coimbatore, India. (Deputed from Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, India.)

G. VINOTHINI

Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, India.

Abstract

Affectively committed faculty are tremendous assets to their companies because they don't waver in the face of alluring outside opportunities. Thus, it's important to comprehend how various organisational elements raise employees' affective commitment. The purpose of the study was to look into how faculty commitment affected deemed universities and higher education institutions. While it is advised for higher education institutions to engage in a diverse workforce, more funds ought to be allocated to possibilities for professional development because these have an impact on affective commitment. The study subthemes that helped or hindered faculty work and learning fell within all of these categories. The psychological, social, cultural, and physical context in which learning takes place and influences faculty motivation and achievement is referred to as the learning environment.

Keywords: Commitment, Faculty, University, Influence, Retention.

1.1. INTRODUCTION

Quality is one of the key tenets of the latest leadership models, which seek to keep up with and adapt to local and global developments. It has drawn a lot of attention. The international community views educational reform and overall excellence as the cornerstones of advancement. One could argue that the true difficulty over the next few decades will be gaining access to total quality. The effectiveness of lecturers is one element that affects how well educational institutions perform. A key component of raising performance in higher education is the role of lecturers. Therefore, lecturers with a strong commitment to their profession are essential to boosting educational achievement. High levels of professional dedication will make academics feel like they belong to the company, which will encourage them to serve with all of their heart and without reservation. This will ultimately increase lecturer performance and help the university realise its mission. Similarly, highly motivated instructors, particularly those whose drive stems from spiritual principles like working earnestly, truly, and without regard to gain or loss, can enhance their own performance, which in turn can enhance the reputation of educational institutions and universities. In higher education, a higher education institution's source of greatness is now its professional dedication. Organisations in higher education that primarily rely on the staff they have to enhance the quality of their courses must pay special attention. A burning desire to maintain professionalism in the context of the organization's goals is referred to as professional commitment. Focus all of your efforts on the organization's behalf, and faculty should believe in and accept organisational goals.

1.2. Literature Reviews

Ahmed (2012) the relationship between workplace Inclusion (WI), Employee Diversity (ED), and Workforce Commitment (WC) is examined in this study. A small number of studies have been conducted about ED, WI, and WC, but there have been prior investigations concerning ED and employee commitment. It's common to hear the terms "diversity," "inclusion," "employee commitment," and "effective work culture" in combination. These are all words that you can see used recently in articles about companies hoping to prosper and differentiate themselves in the twenty-first-century global marketplace. There's a growing emphasis on making workplaces diverse and inclusive in order to provide consumers with excellent services, maintain global competitiveness, and manufacture superior goods.

Boamah (2022) Academic constraints are faced by faculty members; female academics in disciplines such as 'engineering', 'science', 'medicine', and 'nursing' are particularly vulnerable to burnout. The nursing profession is unique in that women continue to predominate it, indicating that a sizable proportion of women are more prone to and/or at greater risk of burnout. The experiences of nursing professors, particularly career researchers, and the variables affecting their retention are still largely unknown. The study investigates the work-life experiences of nursing professors in Canada, specifically focusing on the confluence of work and personal life as well as the factors that affect their retention.

Nyunt (2022) Fair tenure procedures are important to professors and higher education institutions. We investigated how professors who were not granted tenure felt about justice. Regarding equitable justice (impartiality of decisions), the justice of procedures (fairness of handles), and justice in interactions (fairness of relationships and treatment), our 22 participants reported experiencing violations of organisational justice, which they claimed made it more difficult for them to achieve success on their tenure track. In order to comprehend concerns about inequality in advanced education's terms and promotion processes, we examine how gender influences participants' experiences. We do this because we recognise that women and faculty who identify as black, Indigenous, or people of colour face particular challenges when it comes to the tenure track.

Rahman (2023) Pay disparity appears to be a significant issue for private universities in emerging nations. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine how pay equity influences university faculty members' organisational commitment in Bangladesh by utilising the theories of relative deprivation and equity. It employed a structured questionnaire along with the convenience sampling technique. 254 full-time faculty members from Bangladeshi private universities, including professors, associate professors, assistant professors, and professors, participated in the study.

According to Reddy (2023), there is a severe professor shortage in the majority of the nation's higher education institutions. Students bear the brunt of significant instructor attrition without any fault of their own. Nowadays, fresh talent chooses other well-paying occupations and career options, making teaching an unappealing profession. This research article therefore has two goals: first, it will identify the characteristics that influence faculty job happiness and

contentment to students in this knowledge-based economy; second, it will investigate how faculty job satisfaction contributes to student satisfaction.

1.3. Importance

The motive of the study is to show the influence of faculty commitment in deemed universities in Tamil Nadu.

1.4. Statement of the problem

Getting the right pay for work, Satisfaction with the job timings, satisfaction with the working hours, the management is doing well by conducting special classes for students. Satisfaction with the current income, frequent breaks in between working hours, being able to take leave when required, the university gives opportunities to explore other departmental subjects, Handling projects and internships for students gives happiness; the university provides food, transportation, medical, and accommodation facilities, which is the main work, as these many perceptions have been viewed in this study.

1.5. Objective of the study

To study the influence of faculty commitment of the employees of deemed universities of Tamil Nadu.

1.6. Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant difference between the influence of employees and commitments related to deemed universities in Tamil Nadu.

1.7. Research Methodology

Data collection refers to the process of enumeration as well as the recording of results. The correct data is vital to the success of an inquiry; the study examines the respondent's commitment influence in numerous elements, as well as the researcher employing the present study on a real-world issue.

1.8. Sample Design

The approach of convenient samples was used to get the main data. A questionnaire was used to perform a field survey. The employees participating in the trial are using a straight-forward sampling technique, with a sample size of 125 from five selected deemed universities.

1.9. Statistical Tools

The ANOVA and simple percentage analysis have been used to analyze the connection between influence on faculty and their commitment towards work related to deemed universities

1.10. Profile of the respondents

The socio-economic factors significantly influence the HRM of the faculties. The socio-economic factors like age, gender, education income, and marital status of the faculties were collected and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Respondents Profile

Employee Profile		No	Percentage
Age group	26 to 30	22	17.60
	31 to 35	34	27.20
	36 to 40	47	37.60
	Above 40	22	17.60
	Total	125	100.00
Gender	Male	110	88.00
	Female	15	12.00
	Total	125	100.00
Income group	₹.50,000	13	10.40
	₹.50,000 to ₹.1,00,000	40	32.00
	₹. 1,00,000 to ₹.2,00,000	35	28.00
	Above ₹.2,00,000	37	29.60
	Total	225	100.00
Marital Status	Married	71	56.80
	Unmarried	54	43.20
	Total	225	100.00

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 shows the important profile of age since it determines the work exposure, excitement to learn, and experience of the respondents.

According to the inference, the age groups with the highest percentages of respondents are those between 26 and 30 years old (17.60%), 31 to 35 years old (27.20%), and 36 to 40 years old (37.60%).

The respondents are from the age group above 40 years, which is low and constitutes 11.56 percent of the total.

The gender category of respondents shows that 88 percent are male, while 12 percent are female respondents in the study.

Education is the key to the success of institutions in acquiring skills through constant and continuous learning. Possessing a good educational background will benefit from skills both in academics and in HRM.

It shows the highest of 35.56 percent having education in HSC, followed by 24.89 percent having education in undergrad, 21.33 percent having education in SSLC, and 18.22 percent having education in post-graduation in the study.

The highest percentage, 29.60 percent, has an income of over \$2,000,00, while the lowest percentage, 10.40 percent, has an income of \$50,000 or less.

In terms of marital status, married people have the highest respondents at 56.80 percent, and unmarried people have the lowest respondents at 43.20 percent.

1.11. Faculties Commitment and influence

The faculties were asked to specify the influence of commitment and it is presented in Table 1.

Table 2: Faculty Commitment and Influence of Deemed Universities

S. No.	Sources	Always	Usually	Occasionally	Not Usually	Never	Total
1.	The right pay for your work	47	48	10	13	7	125
		37.60	38.40	8.00	10.40	5.60	100.00
2.	Satisfied with the job timings	33	38	14	22	18	125
		26.40	30.40	11.20	17.60	14.40	100.00
3.	Satisfied with the working hours	44	46	7	21	7	125
		35.20	36.80	5.60	16.80	5.60	100.00
4.	Management is doing well by conducting special classes for students.	36	53	5	20	11	125
		28.80	42.40	4.00	16.00	8.80	100.00
5.	Satisfied with the current income	46	47	7	16	9	125
		36.80	37.60	5.60	12.80	7.20	100.00
6.	Frequent breaks in between working hours	51	30	6	23	15	125
		40.80	24.00	4.80	18.40	12.00	100.00
7.	Employees are able to take leave when required	43	33	15	20	14	125
		34.40	26.40	12.00	16.00	11.20	100.00
8.	University gives opportunities to explore other department subjects	41	62	4	10	8	125
		32.80	49.60	3.20	8.00	6.40	100.00
9.	Handling projects and Internship works for students, feeling happy	42	35	14	19	15	125
		33.60	28.00	11.20	15.20	12.00	100.00
10.	University provides food, transportation, medical and accommodation facilities	42	43	8	18	14	125
		33.60	34.40	6.40	14.40	11.20	100.00

Source: *Primary Data*

According to Table 2, the majority of respondents (82.40 percent) concur that the university offers opportunities to study subjects outside of their department, while 76.00 percent concur that the pay is fair, 74.40 percent concur that they are content with their current income, 72.00 percent concur that they are content with their working hours, and 71.20 percent concur that management is doing a good job by offering specialized courses to students.

The university provides facilities (68.00%), frequent breaks in between working hours (64.80%), being able to take leave when required (60.80%), and handling projects and internships for students.

Feeling happy (61.60%) is a moderate level of acceptance among the respondents. However, satisfaction with the job timings (56.80%) is the least significant factor among the respondents.

Figure 1: Employee Commitment

The analysis shows that faculty influence on commitment variables is significant. Hence, there is a relationship between faculty influence and commitment that is rejected. The calculated P value is significant. Therefore, the stated hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3: Regression Weights

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
FaculCom1	<---	F1	1.000				
FaculCom2	<---	F1	1.736	0.243	7.155	***	
FaculCom3	<---	F1	0.979	0.177	5.535	***	
FaculCom4	<---	F1	0.993	0.182	5.444	***	
FaculCom5	<---	F1	1.231	0.194	6.346	***	
FaculCom6	<---	F1	1.077	0.203	5.318	***	
FaculCom7	<---	F1	1.595	0.227	7.040	***	
FaculCom8	<---	F1	1.071	0.168	6.385	***	
FaculCom9	<---	F1	1.191	0.206	5.776	***	
FaculCom10	<---	F1	1.298	0.248	5.225	***	

Source: Computed from primary data

This section of the output illustrates how Amos computes degrees of freedom by doing the following: subtracting the number of different sample moments from the number of distinct parameters that need to be estimated. It is always the case that the number of different sample moments takes into account both the variances and the covariances.

In addition, sample means are taken into consideration while estimating means and intercepts. In the process of determining the number of distinct parameters that need to be evaluated, it is possible to count as a single parameter a number of parameters that are guaranteed to be equivalent to one another. There is no accounting for fixed parameters that have a value that remains constant. The 'number of different parameters to be estimated' may be lower than the total number of regression weights, variances, covariances, means, and intercepts in the model. This is because the model contains all of these variables.

Table 4: CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Default model	30	49.038	25	0.003	1.962
Saturated model	55	0.001	0		
Independence model	10	748.008	45	0.001	16.622

Source: Computed from primary data

The disparity, divided by degrees of freedom, in this model for the default model is $49.038/25 = 1.962$, and the discrepancy, divided by degrees of freedom, in the independence model is $748.008/45 = 16.622$. Assuming the default model is true, the likelihood of obtaining a disparity of 49.038 is .001. It is determined that the CMIN/DF should be less than the required five.

Table 5: Model Fit

	Value	Recommended Value
Chi-Square	832.360	$P > 0.05$
GFI	0.960	≥ 0.90
AGFI	0.911	≥ 0.90
NFI	0.934	≥ 0.90
IFI	0.967	≥ 0.90
TLI	0.938	≥ 0.90
CFI	0.966	≥ 0.90
RMSEA	0.064	≤ 0.08

Source: Computed from primary data

The recommended level of Chi-square value is greater than five, and the present study shows Chi-square values of 832.360, GFI (0.937), AGFI (0.911), NFI (0.934), RFI (0.963), IFI (0.967), TLI (0.938), and CFI (0.960) also show greater than recommended values in investor perceptions towards investments in the present study. The recommended level of RMSEA is less than 0.08, and it also has a good recommended value of 0.064 in the presented study.

1.12. Suggestions of the study

- 1) Deemed universities must give proper respect and eligible promotion to the respected faculty on time; this will be helpful in the retention of knowledgeable staff.
- 2) The university must try to solve the problems of faculty when it comes to professional problems and also provide solutions for long or more working hours.

- 3) Frequent and hourly-based classes must be conducted so that faculty do not feel pressure and stress from taking classes.
- 4) The university should not push faculties to complete the syllabus from time to time or to an hourly-based target. It should be set free or can be made flexible, according to the faculty.

1.13. CONCLUSION

The study about deemed universities can be concluded as follows: that motivation based on values has an affirmative and significant effect on the professional commitment of faculty in universities; that motivation based on values has an affirmative and significant effect on faculty performance at deemed universities; The study's results also show that professional commitment mediates the effect of motivation based on values on the performance of lecturers at deemed universities. The implications of this research are to develop professionalism sustainably by carrying out reflective and communication actions to develop the profession and apply it in the teaching and learning process as a form of good performance or self-performance of faculty, and universities must concentrate on the enhancement of faculties as faculty are the backbone of each and every institution around the world.

References

- 1) Ahmed, A. A., Jain, M. P., & Venkatesh, B. R. (2012) influence of diversity and inclusion initiatives on workforce commitment among faculty members, Volume 26 Issue 10, pp. 112-126.
- 2) Boamah, S. A. (2022). Investigating the work–life experiences of nursing faculty in Canadian academic settings and the factors that influence their retention: Protocol for a mixed-method study. *BMJ open*, Issue 12(1), pp.e-056655.
- 3) Nyunt, G., O'Meara, K., Bach, L., & LaFave, A. (2022), Tenure undone: faculty experiences of organizational justice when tenure seems or becomes unattainable. *Equity & Excellence in Education*, Volume 1(2) pp.1-15.
- 4) Rahman, M. S., Md Som, H., Karim, D. N., & Rahman, M. H. A. (2023), The effect of pay equity on organizational commitment in higher education institutions in Bangladesh. *H. Asibur, The effect of pay equity on organizational commitment in higher education institutions in Bangladesh (October 30, 2023). Rahman, MS, Som, HM, Karim, DN, Rahman, MHA & Karim, MM*, Issue 1, pp.240-252.
- 5) Reddy, J. H. S., & Vallabhaneni, M. (2023), A study of faculty job satisfaction and its impact on student satisfaction in management institutes of nashik district affiliated to university of pune *new research in human resource management & employment welfare*, Issue 12, pp.101.